

An Augmented Reality System for Human Operators in Search and Rescue Missions

1st Mykhailo Dmytrenko
DIBRIS
University of Genova
Genova, Italy
mykhailo.dmytrenko@dibris.unige.it

2nd Carmine Recchiuto
DIBRIS
University of Genova
Genova, Italy
carmine.recchiuto@dibris.unige.it

3rd Antonio Sgorbissa
DIBRIS
University of Genova
Genova, Italy
antonio.sgorbissa@unige.it

Abstract—The need for augmenting human rescuers’ capabilities during the Search and Rescue missions has been expressed by recent disasters. Several works have been done on proposing indoor systems which offer localization and mapping solutions as well as taking advantage of augmented reality (AR) for presenting needed information in the context of emergency situations. In this paper, we propose a system that uses wearable sensors (laser scanner and IMU’s) and a graph-based SLAM algorithm. Furthermore, additional sensors have been integrated into the system to monitor external environmental conditions as well as physiological indicators of the rescuer. Finally, all relevant information is presented through Microsoft HoloLens 2 to help rescuers make better decisions based on a more complete picture of the surroundings and, eventually, facilitate a more efficient and fast way to perform Search and Rescue missions.

Index Terms—Augmented reality, Search and Rescue, Graph-Based SLAM, Wearable Sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of an emergency situation caused by environmental disasters fast and efficient response of the rescue teams is a key element to saving as many lives as possible. In this situation constructing a map with Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping (SLAM) is one of the key elements to a successful operation. Although SLAM techniques are widely adopted in the robotic community and were adapted to the Multi-Agent search and rescue operations in the urban environment ([1],[2]) the usage of SLAM techniques is not limited to robots: a human person may contribute to building a map (and be localized within this map) given that proper information is provided through wearable sensors [3]. The great importance of SLAM algorithms based on wearable sensors may be guessed by disaster zones after earthquakes¹. In such conditions, ground robots may have significant problems in finding a path through the debris and make thought-through decisions based on the state of the environment. On the other hand, human rescuers equipped with wearable sensors, real-time built maps, and extra environmental information may significantly contribute to explore the area faster, potentially saving more lives. For these reasons, this project focuses on designing a system that can help rescuers during the search missions by combining Augmented Reality (AR), outdoor and indoor localization

and mapping, environmental and physiological sensors. As shown in [4] AR technologies have already been used in the context of distress situations. The need for the novel approach to this problem is due to the fact that human SLAM which is applicable to the urban environment is not well-explored. Some companies like Leica² provide mobile SLAM for humans, however, the maps are built offline. Specifically, using the information provided by wearable sensors, the path of each operator (consisting in a sequence of 2D poses) and the map of the area that the operator has already visited (a 2D grid of empty/occupied spaces) can be estimated: by merging all the local maps generated by different operators, a global map can be built up, and visualized in run-time through augmented reality technology such as Microsoft HoloLens 2 to the end of improving the rescuing process. To this aim, mobile sensors are used to track environmental data (temperature, vibrations, etc) and health indicators (heart rate, ECG, respiration rate, etc.) to better assess the situation and allow rescuers to take decisions.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system consists of a helmet endowed with a Hokuyo Laser scanner³ and an IMU, a Microsoft HoloLens 2, environmental sensors Thingy 91⁴, a belt integrating the second IMU, a Wearable wellness system⁵ and a field computer running a Linux operating system, the ROS framework and the Karto-SLAM package for localization and mapping. Figure 1 provides general components overview of the system and how they interact with each other. Thingy91 from Nordic Semiconductor is a battery-operated prototyping system with a multitude of sensors for motion, impact, air quality, etc, and is a cloud solution, meaning that the data can be retrieved with cellular connection data. This way an operator can place several of these kits along the way and be able to track any irregularities at points of interest. Wearable wellness system from Smartex is a fully integrated wearable system specifically designed to continuously monitor a cluster of physiological

¹Latest big earthquake in Italy

²Leica’s backpack mapping solution

³Hokuyo’s laser scanner details

⁴Thingy91 product details

⁵Wearable wellness system overview

parameters while moving. The system communicates the environmental data via Bluetooth with the field computer.

Thanks to the connection between the Microsoft Hololens 2 and the ROS network, the rescuers may visualize on the headset the map being built (possibly by multiple operators), and they may see on-demand environmental data (taken from the Thingy91 sensors) and rescuers' physiological data (thanks to the Wellness wearable system)

In the following sections, we will focus on a specific aspect of the system: a method for improving the mapping and localization system by relying on rescuers' feedback.

Fig. 1. Proposed system components overview

III. INTERVENTIONS ON LOOP CLOSURE

Most of the time, the opportunity to reach a previously visited location (as it happens in Figure 2) occurs after an operator has traveled a long path, which means that the errors accumulated during the exploration can be significantly high. Although the scan matching process keeps correcting the poses at every instant, it is not able to eliminate the error completely: therefore, after a long path, the corrected poses represented by the vertices do not represent reality anymore. In this situation, an optimization algorithm is typically executed to adjust the poses in the whole graph, in order to reduce the error as much as possible. The algorithm is called “loop closure solver” in Karto SLAM and applies optimization techniques in order to compute the configuration of vertex poses that minimizes an overall error function. To help the algorithm close the loops at the correct locations, it has been decided to use human natural capabilities of recognizing the scene, allowing the operator to give a voice input to the system.

To provide additional information about the position of the possible loop closures, it was decided to give a possibility to describe the landmarks which the operator can see around while exploring the area. However, using natural language in this context may be tricky, since operators may use different words to express the same concept. For this reason, a vocabulary list was generated, and in the attempt to arrange and classify all the words in the vocabulary list, Ontologies were used [5]. Moreover, since the network connection might be

disrupted in the event of an emergency situation, the system must be fully operational offline, hence the vocabulary list for the voice recognition method is limited. The words were chosen according to the typical landmarks which are usually seen in the urban environment - in this case, the historical center of Genova.

To allow voice input, Picovoice⁶ has been chosen as a voice recognition software. It is an efficient offline solution that uses compressed neural networks and can work on resource-restrained microcontrollers.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RESULTS

Several tests have already been made in the historical center in Genova, and the result of the mapping system can be seen on Figure 2. However, more experimental data has to be acquired. It has been observed that there are some computational issues with the Karto-SLAM algorithm upon the map becoming big enough. Hence, at the moment newer algorithms like Cartographer are considered. In addition to this, there is ongoing work to conduct SLAM using in-built Microsoft Hololens 2 sensors, and additional tests need to be performed with the integrated system, to properly evaluate to what extent AR instruments may help rescuers in Search and Rescue missions.

The goal of the project is to show a working concept of the AR system which is able to provide needed information to the human rescuers in real-time.

Fig. 2. Generated map

REFERENCES

- [1] Hongling Wang, Chengjin Zhang, Yong Song, and Bao Pang. Master-followed multiple robots cooperation slam adapted to search and rescue environment. *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, 16(6):2593–2608, 2018.
- [2] Xieyuanli Chen, Hui Zhang, Huimin Lu, Junhao Xiao, Qihang Qiu, and Yi Li. Robust slam system based on monocular vision and lidar for robotic urban search and rescue. In *2017 IEEE International Symposium on Safety, Security and Rescue Robotics (SSRR)*, pages 41–47, 2017.
- [3] Carmine Tommaso Recchiuto, Antonello Scalmato, and Antonio Sgorbissa. A dataset for human localization and mapping with wearable sensors. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 97:136–143, 2017.
- [4] Marc Codina, David Castells-Rufas, Jordi Carrabina, Iker Salmon, Néstor Ayuso, Alfonso Guerendiain, and Gonzalo Alvarez. Augmented reality for emergency situations in buildings with the support of indoor localization. *Proceedings*, 31(1), 2019.
- [5] Nicola Guarino, Daniel Oberle, and Steffen Staab. What is an ontology? *Handbook on Ontologies*, pages 1–17, 05 2009.

⁶Picovoice main webpage